

Research Article

Development of a Natural Water Purification System from Agricultural Waste.

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Abstract: Access to clean and safe drinking water remains a major challenge worldwide, particularly in remote, rural, and low-income communities. Traditional water filtration systems can be expensive, difficult to maintain, or inaccessible in areas with limited infrastructure. At the same time, large amounts of agricultural waste are produced and discarded, especially in tropical regions. Coconut husks and Indian-almond (*Terminalia catappa*) leaves are widely available and often treated as waste, even though they have natural properties that could be useful. Improper disposal of this biomass contributes to environmental pollution and waste management issues. Thus, converting these agricultural wastes as fillers and biodegradable Polylactic Acid (PLA) as matrixes, further fabricate filaments that are used to 3D-print water filter components. The objective is to develop a low-cost, easy to produce filter using basic 3D printing and agricultural waste, offering a creative, locally viable solution to multiple challenges. To create usable fibers, the coconut husk and Indian almond leaves are first crushed into powder form to be mixed with PLA. Next, slit-shaped filter components that enhance water flow and eliminate impurities are 3D printed using the composite PLA filament. After being assembled into a filter unit, these components are tested using contaminated water. The effectiveness of the filter is evaluated by looking at the pH, bacteria levels, and clarity of the water. The filters are expected to be long lasting and biodegradable, effectively purifying water and reducing harmful microorganisms. This invention addresses waste pollution and water safety while providing a workable, environmentally responsible solution that communities can utilize to safeguard the environment and enhance public health.

Keywords: agricultural waste; water filtration; 3D printed.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Clean water access is still a problem worldwide, particularly in underprivileged and rural areas. Conventional water filtration techniques can be expensive, energy-intensive, and environmentally damaging. On the other hand, traditional water filtration systems can be expensive, difficult to maintain, or inaccessible in areas with limited infrastructure. This creates serious health risks, including waterborne diseases like cholera and diarrhea, which continue to affect millions every year. The core problem, therefore, is twofold: the lack of affordable and sustainable water purification methods, and the environmental impact of unused agricultural by-products. Existing technologies often do not address both issues at once. By using natural agricultural materials, such as coconut husk and Indian almond (*Terminalia catappa*) leaves, as biofiltration media, this invention offers a

sustainable and affordable solution. These substances are efficient at eliminating contaminants from water because of their inherent antimicrobial and adsorptive qualities (Duwiejah, Adjei & Alhassan, 2024). This method offers an affordable water treatment alternative while promoting environmental sustainability through the repurposing of organic waste. There is a growing need for an innovative solution that is affordable, environmentally friendly, and easy to produce in local settings. Therefore, this research innovation highlights on a system to purifies water using agricultural waste materials that would help provide clean water and reduce environmental pollution by giving new purpose to agricultural waste. Solving this problem can significantly improve public health and support sustainable development in vulnerable communities.

2. MATERIAL & METHOD

2.1 Material

The primary materials used in this study included 50 Indian almond leaves and nine whole coconuts, which were thoroughly cleaned to remove dirt and contaminants. These materials were then air-dried on aluminium foil-lined trays and in an oven at temperature of 60°C for 24 hours. A biodegradable polymer, polylactic acid (PLA) was used as the base material or matrix for the composite filament production. The dried agricultural waste was crushed into powder form, sieved for homogenous particle size and mixed with PLA and extruded into filament using a Twin Screw Extruder (TSE). The filtration unit body was fabricated via fused deposition modelling (FDM) 3D printing using the composite PLA filament prepared. The design of the filtration unit was made using the 3D design software Tinkercad. A container filled with these two-3D printed composite materials was filled with water.

3. EXPECTED OUTCOME

A useful and eco-friendly water filtration system using agricultural waste specifically, coconut husks and Indian almond leaves, is the anticipated result of this innovation. The system is intended to reduce microbial contamination in water and filter out physical contaminants by fusing these natural materials with 3D printing technology. Slits that allow water to pass through while firmly holding the filtering materials in place are printed using specialized filament made from a blend of PLA and agricultural waste.

The filtration unit's body provides a lightweight and replicable structure, having been designed in Tinkercad and printed using the composite PLA. It is expected that this invention will increase the clarity of the water and offer a sustainable substitute for traditional filters. It works particularly well in places where access to potable water is scarce. Although the system is not meant to produce drinking water, it should work well for irrigation and general cleaning. Its performance could be improved and its practical application expanded with more testing and improvement.

4. DISCUSSION

This innovation successfully combines agricultural waste and 3D printing to create a sustainable water filtration system. Coconut husk and Indian almond leaves are examples of natural and biodegradable materials that help absorb pollutants and reduce microbial contamination. By combining these agricultural wastes with polylactic acid (PLA) to create a custom filament, it is possible to 3D print filtration slits that allow water pass through while keeping the filter media.

The main filter body, which was designed with Tinkercad and printed using ordinary PLA, offers a lightweight and flexible structure. By replacing traditional materials like sand and gravel with agricultural waste, the design improves filtration control while reducing environmental impact.

The system is potential for non-drinking uses like cleaning or irrigation is demonstrated by the water's noticeable clarity after filtration. This technique shows how combining natural resources and modern technology can produce affordable, eco-friendly water treatment solutions that are especially useful in resource-constrained environments. Figure 1 shows the water filtration design by using the 3D printed composite filament.

Figure 1. This is a figure.

5. Conclusion

This innovation effectively demonstrates the effective integration of agricultural waste, such as coconut husk and Indian almond leaves, into a 3D-printed water filtration system. By combining natural materials with modern 3D printing technology, it provides a sustainable and ecologically friendly alternative to traditional filtration methods. The precise design features enabled by the custom filament made from PLA and agricultural waste improve water flow and filtration efficiency. The system may effectively reduce microbial contamination in addition to physical contaminants. This approach offers a versatile and cost-effective solution suitable for locations with limited access to clean water. Further testing and development could improve its filtration performance and expand its practical applications.

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References

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